

A LINGUISTIC STUDY OF HISTORICAL WORDS IN ABDULLAH QADIRI'S NOVEL "DAYS GONE BY"

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14045329>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 31th October 2024

Accepted: 05th November 2024

Online: 06th November 2024

KEYWORDS

Historicisms, historical words, descriptive aspect, historical aspect, stylistic tools.

ABSTRACT

In Uzbek linguistics, historical words (historicisms) are the names of past reality, and in the modern language there is no other lexical unit that could replace them. Historical words are not specific to the vocabulary of the period of the language being described, but are found in the temporary use of a unit specific to the vocabulary of the past period. Historical words, in addition to the nominative function, the function of embodying the era, also serve as a methodological tool. This task is one of the main reasons for preserving historicisms in vocabulary. In the novel by Abdullah Kadiri "Past Days" the period of the Kokan Khanate of the 1950-1960s is described. The author effectively uses historical words to reveal the spirit of the time.

INTRODUCTION

"Historical words are old lexical units of the past history of the language, which are used now in connection with the need to name the reality of the past (historicism)" [1]. The famous scientist Sh. Rakhmatullaev, the author of this quote, as well as the Uzbek linguist L. Abdullaeva [2] in their research work provided detailed information about historical words (historicisms). In the "Lexicology of the Uzbek Language", which is considered an academic publication, our scientists touched upon historical words [3].

Historical words have the following linguistic features:

- historical words are a phenomenon that differs sharply from mutual archaisms. Accordingly, they should be assessed separately, and not together;
- historicisms are usually the only name for the reality to which they relate;
- in the archaic type of obsolete vocabulary is a stylistic synonym for a lexical unit that is considered normal today. The same applies to historicism;
- historical words are singular and later relate to this lexical unit itself;
- historical words, in addition to the nominative function, the function of embodying the era, also serve as a stylistic tool.
- historicisms are equivalent to the loss of a certain lexical unit from the dictionary: the loss of reality makes the lexical unit, which is the name of this reality, unnecessary (for example: **Bek**

(turkic) - *Among some Turkic peoples, statesmen, cities or regional governors during the khanate; a high administrative title during the khanate and position.*

- it is noticeable that historical words have certain common features between languages;
- historical words are interpreted primarily taking into account the history of social, political, cultural development of society (extralinguistic factor); therefore, their origin is relatively easy to explain;
- historical words rarely return to the vocabulary as a normal lexical unit, when they return, their lexical meaning changes radically, i.e. they are updated in meaning, as if they become a new lexical unit (for example: *vazir*- minister, *mahkama*-cabinet: Cabinet of Ministers).

Literature Review. The novel by Abdullah Kadiri "The Days Gone By" describes the events of the 50-60s of the 19th century, that is, the time when the king of the Kokand Khanate, Khudayarkhan, ruled. At that time, the khanate was going through a period of upheaval, disagreements, conflicts, economic and political decline. The events of the novel take place in Tashkent, in Margilan. Abdullah Kadiri convincingly and vividly reflects the tyranny of the khans, the idleness of officials, the treachery and hypocrisy of the courtiers of that time. The author effectively uses historical words to reveal the spirit of the time. The work is distinguished, first of all, by its extraordinary vitality. The novel is written in a charming language, and from the language of the work it is clear that he knows the rich and wonderful language of the people very well. In the novel, the author used more than 60 historical words. We will try to define them, as we have already said above, on the and **historical and descriptive front.**

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

1. Historical words on the historical (diachronic) front. In the novel "Days Gone By" the author effectively used historical words that were in use at the time the work was written, but are considered socio-political vocabulary units, the use of which dates back to the "new" era. The following historical words can be included in a sentence: **Beklarbegi** (turkic) - *a high administrative rank and position during the khanate; Hakim of the region and large cities* (p. 43) [4]; **Bekach** (turkic) -, *lady, mistress - the wife or daughter of the bek and, in general, rulers and nobles*: "Here is my *bekachi*," Tuybeka said with a laugh. Also in the TSUYA (Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language) the lexeme "bekach" is obsolete in the sign it is mentioned as "a word used to respectfully address women": - Don't cry, *mistress*, - said Tuybeka (72); "Oh, I would like to see this groom! You knew how handsome he was, how smart he was, my *mistress*" (p. 73); **Ilg'or** (arabic) - *the front line of an army, the vanguard*: When the *vanguard* of Musulmonkul approached Chirchik,... (p. 282); **Bekvachcha** (turkic) - *a child born to a bek*: ... the bek and the *bekvachcha* recognized him (56); **Xon** (turkic, mongolian) - *khan, the absolute ruler of a smaller state*: he killed the governors sent by the *khan* to collect zakat! (p. 57); - If not, will the residents not write a complaint to the *khan*? (p. 40); The people of Tashkent brought the *khan* and the army of Kokand into the city with great honor and a party for three days (p. 256); - As soon as they heard the name of *Khudayarkhan*, they stood up and sat down to bow to him again (p 115). *Kan* (S.E. Malov, "NDP", p. 411), "Devanu lugatit turk" - *khan, kan* in kyrgyz (K.K. Yudakhin, "KRS", p. 338), L.Z. Budagov - mongolian *qaan*, which is an abbreviated form of the word word (L. Z. Budagov, "SSTN", p. 152); **Tanga** (turkic) - *coins*: To give the beki of the fortress a kimkhab robe, to the yuzbashi a silk robe, and to the other guys

a gift of three *coins*! (p. 469); **Yasov** (turkic) - *a row, squad*: ... soldiers in uniform, whom I saw in Tashkent ... - *yasov* (p. 132); **Sipoh** - (persian-tadjik) - *khan, official, warrior, soldier, sepoy, who served in the emir's palace for a long time*; **Biyltik** (turkic) - *elder of the clan - in this place - rule*: After the death of my mother-in-law, my next wife, who remained in power in her hands, began to provide for me indecently (p. 216); **Ulamo, fuzalo** (arabic) - *scholars*: by order of Azizbek, yesterday all the Tashkent residents gathered in pod urde, in this gathering there are *ulamo and fuzalo* (p. 57). In arabic, the main consonant suffixes are (-un) and (-u). In the uzbek language, this suffix (-u) was dropped in arabic assimilations and assimilated in the form of "ulama". The word "ulama" is "a'limun" the plural form of the word "alimun", which means "scholars". There are many "broken" plural forms in arabic. Of these, there are relatively many words derived from the "broken" plural forms [fuzala' + u], [ulama' + u], assimilated into the uzbek language. However, in linguistics it is often observed that words adopted in the plural are used in the singular form in the host uzbek language. For example, *fukarolar* (citizens), *ancestor* (grandfathers), *descendant* (children). "ulama" means "scientists" and means "a person engaged in science". After the adoption of Islam, the word "ulama" was used primarily to denote "persons engaged in religious knowledge" and remained so in common parlance. Since the beginning of the 20th century (including the 1930s, emphasis ours. M.K.) and to this day, the word "ulama" has been and is used in the meaning of "scientists", to denote "persons engaged in worldly knowledge". For example: The wise words of the great enlightener Ishakhan Ibrat have a deep meaning: "Who will reform the nation?" "When the nation is motivated, the nation will definitely find reform" [5].

Qozi (*justice*) - even if he has a thought to call his wife to *justice* (p. 272); When Zainab's madness was confirmed by *justices* and doctors, the punishment was toughened (p. 381); **Charoqchi** (*torchbearer, turkic*) - The *torchbearer* of the Horde lit a torch near the gate, and the Horde caught fire inside (p. 90); **Hudaichi, udaychi** - *means adjutant, usually before the arrival of the khan he is the one who warns the people*: Azizbek appointed himself an *adjutant*; - *Adjutant, adjutant* Suleyman - they said (p. 102); **Yuzboshi** (turkic) - *leader*: That is, Aftab, he met women of Tashkent from *yuzbashi* (*leader*), *ponsadboshi, qurbashi* with women of the Horde and received unexpected honor and respect from some of them (p. 341); **Qo'rboshi** (turkic): - Muhammad Rajab *qo'rboshi* shakes his head and looks at Niyaz kushbegi:... (p.287); - The *qo'rbashi* shouted bitterly to this illogical answer... - funny (p.87); *Qo'rbashi* ignored the visitor's greeting... (p.85); **Kudingchi** - *one who gives finishing to fabric*: Marayim *kudingchi* was like a relaxed person, and her neighbors were also trying to dissuade him... (p.190); **Munodi** (turkic) - *a herald*: *Munodi* shouted to the kipchak boys who wanted to run away from the leader (p.282); **Mirshab** (arabic, *shortened form of mir-amir*) - *persian, shab (night) - night (evening) amir*: Qutidar, brought to the qorbashi court for interrogation by the *mirshabs* (p. 266); **Mingboshi** (turkic) - *leader*: Otabbay qushbegi - one of the best of the kipchak beks. This man was the ruler of Margilan between 1263-1267. After Musulmankul, he was appointed in his place by *mingbashi* (p. 327); **Ponsadboshi** - *is a military act, a title that led an army of five hundred people (among the military ranks in the Kokan khanate, the title was higher than mingbashi)*: Until then, *ponsadbashi*, killed by reading the letter, was well impressed by the letter (234); After Otabek's words, *ponsadboshi* looked at the kushbegu, as if saying: "Come on, let's finish" (244); **Qushbegi** (turkic) - He qurbashi shook his head and

looked at Niyaz *qushbegi* (p. 287); - Otabboy *qushbegi* just returned from home. Meanwhile, korbashi entered and bowed to him... (p.92); **Yasovul** (mongolian) - *an armed guard, watchman, disciplinarian, security guard, minor official walking next to high officials* - "Ahmed *yasovul* and Kara Akhmad yurtchi again sent to the beks of Kabul..." (Baburnoma, p. 149.11, p. 210) and others.

The results of the study show that the quoted historical words directly indicate the names of persons in the socio-political life of that time.

In our work, we also use historical words of the diachronic front associated with the state system, names of places associated with the state system, technology, currency, the military, weapons and other aspects associated with socio-political life. Here are some examples:

O'rda (mongolian) - *a fortress where the rulers live, resident: ... by order of Azizbek yesterday all the Tashkent residents gathered under the horde, in this gathering there are scientists and fuzalo; ... (57); Orda is built on the city wall in the area of "Yormozor" (88); Orda means the residence of the rulers, - "to rise up": or+ut+orut+uorutu+ortu+ordu+orda (E.V. Sevortyan, "ESTYA", p.427) [6].*

Zindon (persian) - *dungeon:, - so you both will remain in prison until the truth is revealed (96); ... - if you enter three or four steps from the threshold of the gate, you will feel one of the dungeons of Bukhara (51).*

Mahkama (arabic) - *court, office [7]: Kutidar, whom the mirshabs brought for interrogation to the ruler's court (p.266);*

Yorlig' - TSUYA (explanatory dictionary of the uzbek language - 2006-2008) - *an official document, a decree on granting a charter, title, suyurgul, etc.: Azizbek began to leave the labels and decrees of Kokand without compliments (208).*

Simkor (persian) - *wages paid to apprentices based on the results of their work: - No, no, - laughed master Alim, - I'm not like you, I'm not an egg in the workshop, I would believe you, they don't want to pay wages (236);*

Tanga - (turkic) - *a coin, a monetary unit, 15 tyns in the Bukhara Khanate, 20 tyns in the Kokan Khanate: My decision is this: from tomorrow you will tax the country in thirty-two coins (125);*

Shashvar (persian) - *military weapons:... on the reverse side the obstacle was full of people holding shashvars, guns, daggers and spears in their hands (127).*

2. Historical words on the descriptive (synchronic) front. It is known that the work covers the 1950s and 1960s of the XIXth century. It should be noted here that the lexemes used in prose works (considered new at that time), now obsolete, were used mainly to reflect the spirit and color of the time. It is noted that such lexemes are used for this purpose more in the speech of the characters than in the speech of the authors. Another thing is that the work is mainly aimed at describing Uzbek life and highlighting the spirit of the times, and most of the lexemes have fallen out of use, that is, they have become historical words. They are included in the sentence of historical words on the synchronic (figurative) front. To confirm our opinion, let us turn to the examples: **To'p, to'pchi** (turkic) - *artillery, artilleryman: another - a total of three artillery were located in the northwest direction. On this hill there were permanent artillerymen and guards (p. 471); **Muzaxana** (persian) - *museum: The house**

was richly furnished, as if it gave the impression of a *muzaxana* (namely, a museum) (67); **Qutidor** - *official*: Akhmedbek, who was the only brother of Oftoboim, who did not find another man in the family of *qutidars*, also spent most of his life in Kokandami and Khujand (p. 87); - We will not get acquainted with this person a second time, because this person met with the reader - Mirzakarim *qutidar* (p. 51); - Otabek looked at Mirzakarim *qutidar* again (p. 38)

DISCUSSION

Many historical words are used in the work, which reflects the following two situations: a) the works were considered historical words at the time of their creation, i.e. historical words of the diachronic front (lexical units used before the mid-19th century); b) words that were considered neologisms or were in active use at the time of the creation of the works, but have now become historical words, i.e. obsolete words on the synchronic front (lexical units that appeared after the second half of the 19th century). The relevant sources suggested that historical words perform a methodological function, and it was shown that there are few examples of the use of historical words in our object of study. For example: **Yo'lak zindoni - corridor priseon** - Having got out of the *corridor dungeon*, a person goes to the bank of a large stream, into the yard, like a herd, and rests pleasantly (51). In this place, the author used the lexeme "dungeon" as a methodological task.

CONCLUSION

The work also uses historical word forms. For example: **yog'mur** (p. 171) - *rain* (for months I cry like *rain*); **jekirdi** (p. 204, p. 300) - *yank*; **kiprak** (p. 205) - *eyelash* (p. 10); **shirni** (p.10-bet) – **shinni** - *jam*, **miqroziladi (miqroz - small scissors)** (p.199): ... we cut off the end of a candle, straighten it; **joblagan edi** (p.182) – *intended*. In this way, the writer expressed the spirit of the era and the environment and preserved the principle of creating historical color. The words **mushovur, qutidor, qushbegi, qorboshi, hudaychi** in the work do not have synonyms in our modern language, they are included in the structure of the language of the work as the only names of these objects, giving an idea of the old style. speech. As a result of the analysis, it was established that almost all historical words in the work consist of Turkish words.

References:

1. Rakhmatullaev Sh. Historicism // Reference source, 164- Ibid., pp. 163-164.
2. Abdullaeva L. Lexical stylistics... -P. 54-55. Lexicology of the Uzbek language, pp. 151-152.
3. Lexicology of the Uzbek language, pp. 151-152.
4. The numbers in the following examples are taken from the novel by Abdullah Kadiri "Otkan kunlar". Abdullah Kadiri. Past days. Tashkent, Info Capital Group, 2017. (based on the materials of the 1926, 1933 editions).
5. From a speech at an expanded meeting of the Council of Spirituality and Education of the Republic on December 22, 2023, chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev.
6. Sh. Rakhmatullaev "Etymological dictionary of the uzbek language (Turkic languages), T., 2000, p. 485.

7. Currently, the term for the court is “council of ministers, a government structure; it has again come to be used in the sense of government: Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.